

Comparison of Serum Visfatin Level in Normal Weight, Overweight and Obese Individuals**Sudipta Kumari Onkar¹, Rasmita Kumari Padhy², Nirupama Devi³, Bishnupriya Panda⁴, Sucheta Panda⁵, Manaswini Das⁶, Subrat Kumar Pradhan⁷**¹Senior Resident, Department of Biochemistry, MKCG MCH, Berhampur, Odisha, India²Professor & Head, Department of Biochemistry, SRM MCH, Odisha, India³Professor & Head, Department of Biochemistry, MKCG MCH, Berhampur, Odisha, India⁴Senior Resident, Department of Biochemistry, MKCG MCH, Odisha, India⁵Associate Professor, Department of Biochemistry, MKCG MCH, Berhampur, Odisha, India⁶Senior Resident, Department of Biochemistry, MKCG MCH, Berhampur, Odisha, India⁷Post Graduate Trainee, Department of Biochemistry, MKCG MCH, Berhampur, Odisha, India

Received: 25-02-2024 / Revised: 23-03-2024 / Accepted: 20-04-2024

Corresponding Author: Nirupama Devi

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Adipose Tissue Is Not Only The Storehouse Of Fats And Energy But Also A Major Endocrine Organ Secreting Adipocytokines. Adipocytokines Play An Important Role In Regulation Of Food Intake & Body Weight, Insulin Sensitivity, Inflammation And Vascular Haemostasis. Visfatin Is A Novel Adipokine (52kda) Predominantly Secreted From Visceral Fat. It Shows Insulin-Mimetic Effects Which Correlate With Overweight & Obesity. Our Aim Is To Compare Serum Visfatin Level In Normal Weight, Overweight & Obese Individuals.

Materials & Methods: This Is A Cross-Sectional Comparative Study Of Total 162 Adults Between Age Group Of 20-60yrs Including Both The Sexes. All The Individuals Are Divided Into 3 Groups With 54 Subjects Each As Per Bmi. 3ml Of Whole Blood Is Collected With Informed Consent From All Individuals. Serum Visfatin Level Is Analyzed By Elisa. All Data Are Presented As Mean (M) & Standard Deviation (\pm Sd). Statistical Analysis To Be Done Using Spss Version 20. The Values Are Considered Significant At $P < 0.05$.

Results: Fasting Serum Visfatin Level Is Increased In Overweight (100.8 ± 29.9 pg/ml) & Obese Individuals (129.1 ± 21.4 pg/ml) As Compared To Normal Weight Subjects (82.4 ± 26.5 pg/ml) Which Is Statistically Significant ($P < 0.012$).

Conclusion: Serum Visfatin Is Elevated In Overweight & Obese Individuals Compared To Normal Individuals. The Significant Increase Level Of Visfatin In Obese May Be Used As A Diagnostic And Prognostic Biomarker For Insulin Resistance And Metabolic Syndrome.

Keywords: Adipokines, Visfatin, Bmi &, % Bfm.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Obesity is defined as an abnormal growth of adipose tissue due to an enlargement of fat cell size (hypertrophic obesity) or an increase in fat cell number (hyperplastic obesity) or a combination of both [1]. Moreover, obesity is one of the most prevalent non-communicable disease with major health concerns. This is a condition characterised by the excessive accumulation of fat in the visceral and subcutaneous regions. The excess

weight gain occurs when energy intake exceeds the energy consumption. This excess weight is stored in adipose tissue consisting of adipose cells or adipocytes with an incredible capacity to store the excess energy in the form of lipids.

Obesity is one of the most common & neglected, public health problem in both developed and developing countries as per World Health Organization (WHO) [2]. Obese individuals have higher rates of mortality and morbidity as compared to non-obese individuals [3]. Obesity is the leading preventable cause of death worldwide and serious public health concern of the 21st century.

In India, more than 135 million individuals were affected by obesity.

According to World Health Organisation Statistics Report 2016, 1.9 billion adults, 18yrs and older, were overweight, of these over 650 million were obese [4]. In 2019, more than 38.2 million children under 5 years of age were overweight or

obese. [5] India with 1.2 billion people is now the second-most populous country in the world and is currently experiencing rapid epidemiological transition from under nutrition to obese. [6] According to, ICMR-INDIAB study 2015, prevalence rate of obesity varies from 11.8% - 31.3%. The prevalence of overweight will more than double among Indian adults aged 20-69 years

between 2010 and 2040, while the prevalence of obesity will triple. Specifically, the prevalence of overweight and obesity will reach 30.5% (27.4-34.4%) and 9.5% (5.4-13.3%) among men and 27.4% (24.5-30.6%) and 13.9% (10.1-16.9%) among women respectively by 2040. [7]

Who Classification of Adults According to Bmi

Classification	BMI	Risk of Comorbidites
Underweight	<18.50	Low
Normal range	18.5-24.99	Average
Overweight	>25.00	High
Pre-obese	25.00-29.99	Increased
Obese class I	30.00-34.99	Moderate
Obese class II	35.00-39.99	Severe
Obese class III	>40.00	Very Severe

Visfatin is a novel adipocytokine predominantly secreted from visceral fat and found in Liver, muscle, bone marrow, lung, heart, placenta, kidney tissue and peripheral lymphocytes.[8] Visfatin corresponds to a protein identified previously as pre- B cell colony enhancing factor (PBEF), a 52-kilodalton cytokine expressed in lymphocytes. [9]. Visfatin/ PBEF gene consists of 11 exons & 10 introns spanning 34.7kb, is located on chromosome 7q22. [10] Visfatin (NAMPT), with its two isoforms, the extracellular (eNAMPT) and intracellular (iNAMPT) forms, is crucial for NAD biosynthesis, with the higher activity of the extracellular form. NAD is required for various processes, including metabolic processes, glucose stimulated insulin secretion, cell survival, cell cycle control, and apoptosis [11].

Circulating visfatin levels are closely correlated with WAT (White Adipose Tissue) accumulation, visfatin mRNA levels increase in the course of adipocyte differentiation, and visfatin synthesis is regulated by several factors, including glucocorticoids, TNF- α , IL 6, and GH6. Visfatin plasma concentrations and visceral visfatin mRNA expression correlated with measures of obesity.

Visfatin were shown to be increased in females with visceral obesity. Decrease in circulating visfatin was found in morbidly obese women who lost more than 20% of their BMI [12], also increased plasma Visfatin concentrations in morbidly obese subjects are reduced after gastric banding [13]. These studies show that more the BMI (obesity) more the visfatin levels and levels decrease after weight loss.

Visfatin binds to & activates the insulin receptor exerting Insulin-mimetic effects which correlate with over weight and Obesity.[14] Increased visfatin levels in Obesity may indicate a regulatory response to keep blood glucose levels stable. Plasma levels of visfatin associated to a

greater extent with amount of visceral fat than that of adipose tissue. [15] Recent research has demonstrated that visfatin reduces insulin-stimulated glucose metabolism in skeletal muscle causing Insulin resistance. [16]

Studies have shown that an increased level of visfatin is associated with IR and T2DM [16,17], metabolic syndrome (MetS) [18], polycystic ovary syndrome [19] and T2DM-associated complications such as cardiovascular [20,21], cerebrovascular [22, 23], and renal [24, 25, 26] diseases.

Materials & Methods

Place of Study: The study was conducted in department of Biochemistry, M.K.C.G. Medical College and Hospital, Berhampur, Odisha. Samples were collected from medical staffs and colleagues, attendant of patients, MBBS and nursing students with approval of Institutional ethical committee and informed consent was taken.

Study Period: February 2021- November 2022.

Selection of Study Population: A total of 162 individuals were included in this study in the age group of 20-50 years, including both sexes. All the individuals were classified into three category according to body mass index (BMI) – Normal weight, Overweight, and Obese in accordance with recommendations of World Health Organizations and waist circumference (WCF) \geq 90cms in men and \geq 80cms in women and waist hip ratio (WHR) \geq 1.0 in men and \geq 0.85 in women. [27]

Healthy Individuals Group I (GP-I): Age, sex and BMI matched apparently healthy individual recruited as controlled with normal body weight, BMI-(18.0-24.99)

Overweight Individuals Group II (GP-II): Individuals with BMI –(25.00-29.99)

Obese Individuals Group III (GP-III):
Individuals with BMI - ≥ 30.00

Inclusion Criteria

1. Age group between 20- 50years
2. Both the sex
3. Normal weight, Overweight & Obese individuals.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Age below < 20yrs & ≥ 50 years.
2. Diabetes mellitus.
3. Hypertension.
4. Thyroid disease.
5. Drug history like steroid, OCP.
6. Any chronic illness like T.B., Liver, kidney and heart diseases.
7. Pregnancy.
8. Smoking and alcoholism.
9. PCOS.

Collection of Blood Sample: 5ml of whole blood was collected. Two ml of blood was kept for estimation of fasting plasma glucose. Three ml of blood was kept in serum separator tube for two hours at room temperature and then centrifuged at approximately 2000 to 3000 rpm for 15 to 20 minutes for Visfatin assay. by ELISA kit. The

serum samples were brought to room temperature before starting the assay.

Estimation of Human Serum Visfatin: Visfatin is a recently described adipokine preferentially secreted by visceral adipose tissue (VAT) with insulin mimetic properties. Serum Visfatin was estimated using the commercially available ELISA kit marketed by Abbkine, Inc. with the Catalog number KTE62221.

Assay principle: Human serum Visfatin ELISA Kit employs a two-site sandwich ELISA to quantitative Visfatin in samples. An antibody specific for Human Visfatin has been pre-coated onto a micro plate. Standards and samples are pipetted into the wells and any Visfatin present is bound by the immobilized antibody. After removing any unbound substances, HRP conjugated Visfatin detection antibody is added to the wells. Following a wash to remove any unbound HRP reagent, a Chromogen solution is added to the wells and colour develops in proportion to the amount of Visfatin bound in the initial step. The colour development is stopped and the intensity of the colour is measured.

Absorbance of Visfatin Standard Solutions and Their Concentration

Standard	Concentration (pg/ml)	Absorbance in nm
SD1	0	0.0680
SD2	25	0.1278
SD3	50	0.1972
SD4	100	0.3925
SD5	200	0.7919
SD6	400	1.2302
SD7	800	1.7527

Standard Curve for Visfatin

Result:**Table 1: Age and sex distribution in study groups**

Age group	Normal weight			Overweight			obese		
	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total	Male	Female	Total
20-35	10	14	24	7	21	28	8	13	21
36-50	12	18	30	12	14	26	16	17	33
total	22	32	54	19	35	54	24	30	54

This table shows age and sex distribution of all three groups. All the groups were divided into two groups according to age i.e. 20-35 years and 36-50 years. Maximum cases were within the range of 36- 50 years. Percentage of females was more in comparison to males.

Table-2: Comparison of anthropometric data in study groups

Parameters	Normal Weight (n=54) MEAN+SD	Overweight (n=54) MEAN +SD	Obese (n=54) MEAN +SD	'P' Value
Age	37.6±10.8	36.4±9.3	36.8±9.2	0.862
Height	157.7±8.4	157.4±6.7	157.5±8.9	0.980
Weight	59.2±10.3	69.5±7.2	81.7±11.3	0.000**
BMI	22.8±1.6	27.6±1.3	32.8±2.7	0.000**
BFM	24.7±8.7	34.5±8.5	43.4±11.4	0.000**
WC	82±10.7	90.03±7.01	106.4±11.4	0.000**
HC	93.9±7.10	102.6±6.1	110.3±11.3	0.000**
WHR	0.87±0.04	0.88±0.06	0.96±0.10	0.000**

P value- <0.05* is significant

The above table depicts about comparison of demographic data of the three groups. The mean and standard deviation of AGE, HEIGHT, WEIGHT, BMI, %BFM, WHR, WC & HC has been tabulated. The data were compared between the three groups. The Mean ± SD of demographic parameters of Overweight and Obese groups are more as compared to Normal weight group which is statistically significant, p<0.05.

Table 3: Comparison of serum visfatin in study groups

Parameter	Normal Weight (n=54) MEAN+SD	Overweight (n=54) MEAN+SD	Obese (n=54) MEAN+SD	'P' Value
Serum Visfatin (pg/ ml)	82.4±26.5	100.8±29.9	129.1±21.4	0.012**

*p<0.05 is significant.

Graph 1:

Table-3 and graph 1 showed the mean serum Visfatin values in normal weight, overweight and obese individuals. The values were compared in the three study groups.

Discussion

Obesity and overweight are defined as a systemic disease that shows excessive and abnormal

accumulation of body fat leading to adverse health effect. Obesity imposes devastating health and financial tolls on individuals and society [3]. Obesity has reached epidemic proportions and is a major contributor to the global burden of chronic diseases and disability [28] [4]. Obese people are at a risk of various health issues which can lead to their further morbidity and mortality [29]. In the present study, we have taken 162 healthy individuals. They were grouped into 3 categories according to BMI as normal weight, overweight and obesity. We compared serum Visfatin in cases and controls.

Age and Sex Distribution of Cases and Controls

In the study, all the individuals were again divided into two age groups 20-35yrs and 36-50years. Maximum cases and controls were within the ranges of 36-50 years. The prevalence of obesity was more in females as compared to males (Table-1).

F Garawi. et al. (2014) also had a similar finding in their case control study in which prevalence of obesity shows gendered patterning with greater prevalence and greater heterogeneity in women than in men ($P < 0.001$) [30]

Reem T. Atawia. et al. (2019) had a similar finding in their case control study in which prevalence of obesity in females was higher than males. [31]

K. Sarvottam et al. (2020) also had a similar finding in their case –control study in Varanashi, India in which prevalence of obesity in females was higher than in males. [32]

Shahrukh Khan. et al. (2021) showed that the prevalence of obesity was higher in females than in male. [33]

Women had higher mean value of BMI whereas men had lower and it unquestionably proposes that female gender involves in weight gain and obesity among women. [34] High prevalence of obesity in females may be due to eating food habits, stress, physical inactivity & hormonal imbalance. Women have a higher tendency to accumulate abdominal visceral fat as compared to Men. [35] The accumulation of abdominal visceral fat in women, which is a strong independent predictor of mortality, is mainly due to the higher dietary fat uptake by their abdominal visceral fat. [36]

Anthropometric Parameters of Cases and Controls

In the present study, we observed the mean of demographic parameters like Weight(Kg), BMI(kg/m²), %BFM, Waist circumference (cm), Hip circumference (cm), and Waist Hip Ratio (WHR) in healthy overweight & obese individuals were significantly higher as compared to healthy normal weight individuals. The Mean±SD of BMI

is (32.8±2.7) in obese (27.6±1.3) in overweight and (22.8±1.6) in normal weight individuals. The Mean±SD of %BFM is (43.4±11.4) in obese, (34.5±8.5) in overweight and (24.7±8.7) in normal weight individuals. The Mean±SD of WHR is (0.96±0.10) in obese, (0.88±0.06) in overweight and (0.78±0.04) in normal weight individuals which were statistically significant, $p < 0.05$. (Table-2)

The study done by Seema Dhuria. et al. (2014) carried a study on women (n=100) in Rajasthan, India. They found that the mean ± S.D of BMI (kg/m²) in obese women (29.03± 3.73), WCF (96.58 ± 9.43) and WHR (0.93 ± 0.06) were significantly higher than non-obese woman BMI (21.29± 2.61), WCF (78.37 ± 13.77) and WHR (0.84 ± 0.73) which was statistically significant, $p < 0.05$. [37]

Study done by Fatemeh A et al. (2015) conducted upon 13 adult obese male in Tehran, found that Mean ± S.D of BMI in healthy obese individuals (31.27 ± 1.89) was significantly higher than non-obese individuals BMI (23.01 ± 0.29) with $p < 0.001$ & was similar to our findings. [38] Study done by Babu SV et al. (2017) conducted upon 80 adult obese male attending the master health checkup program at Sri Ramchandra Medical college & Research Institute, India found that the Mean±S.D of BMI (32.5±2.40) in healthy obese male was significantly higher than non-obese male BMI (21.80 ± 1.6) with $p < 0.001$ & was similar to our findings. [39]

Study conducted by R. Kutulu. et al, (2017) on age and sex matched 300 obese individuals found that the Mean ± S.D of BMI (35.39±4.38) and WCF (105.45±14.36) in obese. The Mean±S.D of BMI (25.19± 1.62) and WCF (87.56±10.78) in non-obese. They found the anthropometrical parameters like BMI and WCF in obese were elevated as compared to non-obese which was statistically significant, $p < 0.001$ & was similar to our findings. [40]

The study done by F Kabir. et al. (2018) carried a study on women (n=90) in Dhaka. They found that the Mean± S.D of BMI (Kg/m²) in obese women (28.4±3.5), WC (93.5±7.7), HC (102.2±7.3), %BFM (32.8±6.0) were significantly higher than normal weight women BMI (20.8±1.9), WC (81.0±7.3), HC (89.3±5.8), and BFM (23.5±5.0) which was statistically significant, $p < 0.05$. [41]

Study done by Mallick A.K. et al., (2018) on 200 participants of Rohilakand, U.P found that Mean±S.D of BMI in healthy obese individuals (31.27±1.89) was significantly higher than non-obese individuals BMI (23.01±0.29) with $p < 0.05$ which was similar to our finding. [42] Anthropometric measurements are surrogate measures of body fat and better predictors of overweight and obesity. The cause of

increased BMI, WCF, HC, % BFM and WHR might be due to sedentary lifestyle, pro-inflammatory state and genetic predisposition in obese individuals. [43][44]

Mean Serum Visfatin Level in Cases and Controls

In the present study, the (Mean \pm SD) Visfatin level was recorded as (129.1 \pm 21.4) pg/ml in obese individuals, (100.8 \pm 29.9) pg/ml in overweight individuals which were increased as compared to normal weight individuals (82.4 \pm 26.5) pg/ml which was statistically significant $p < 0.05$. (Table4, Graph-1)

Study conducted by Jurdana Met al. (2013) includes 48 normal weight & obese individuals found that baseline levels of fasting Visfatin were significantly higher in overweight subjects compared to normal weight subjects (4.1 \pm 0.6ng/ml vs 1.8 \pm 0.6 ng/ml for males and 4.4 \pm 0.5 ng/ml vs 2.5 \pm 0.5 ng/ml) for females which was statistically significant $p < 0.001$. [45]

Study conducted by Nourbakhsh, Met al.(2015) includes 73 Iranian normal weight and obese individuals found that (Mean \pm SD) of Visfatin (5.4 \pm 1.2) ng/ml which were more in obese individuals as compared to normal weight individuals (3.9 \pm 1.0) ng/ml, which was statistically significant $p < 0.001$. [46]

Study conducted by F Kabir. et al.(2018) includes 50 overweight subjects who had no disease condition and 42 controls found that (Mean \pm SD) of Visfatin (7.4 \pm 4.2) ng/ml were higher in overweight subjects in comparison to normal weight individuals (4.2 \pm 4.0)ng/ml which was statistically significant ($p < 0.000$). [41]

Study conducted by Souvannavong-Vilivong Xet al.(2019) in Bangkok, Thailand involved 70 normal weight and obese individuals found higher value of (Mean \pm SD) of serum Visfatin (9.18 \pm 3.04) ng/ml in obese individuals as compared to normal weight (4.33 \pm 3.01) ng/ml, which was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$). [47]

In the cross-sectional study conducted by Alnowihi SMet al. (2020) 83 healthy Saudi women of different body weights were recruited between 2014 and 2016, from King Abdulaziz University staff and students. The participants were divided into the following three groups according to their body mass indexes (BMIs): 35 obese women(42%) (29.0 \pm 4.9 years old), 15 overweight women (18%) (23.6 \pm 3.4 years old), and 33 lean women (39.76%) (22.87 \pm 2.64 years old).He found that (Mean \pm SD) of serum Visfatin was (32.6 \pm 3.1) in obese group, (24.1 \pm 5.7) in overweight groups which was higher in comparison to (11.4 \pm 1.4) in normal weight individuals and it was statistically significant, ($p < 0.001$). [48]

Study conducted by Khanna D et al. (2022) includes 57 normal weight & obese individuals found that (Mean \pm SD) of Visfatin (34.2 \pm 13.4) ng/ml were higher in obese groups in comparison to normal weight groups (13.3 \pm 7.0), which was statistically significant $p < 0.001$. [49]

Elevated levels of visfatin have been linked to increased levels of inflammatory markers such as IL-6, IL-8, C-reactive protein, and monocyte chemotactic protein-1 [50], endothelial dysfunction and increase in oxidative stress [51]. These findings point to the existence of an average physiological level of visfatin at which it is properly controlled and fulfils its physiological functions, as well as a threshold level at which its pathological consequences occur.

The significance of visfatin in the pathogenesis of IR and its associated consequences reflects the potential utility of visfatin as an early biomarker for IR in high-risk patients, especially obese adults. [52]

Obesity is closely associated with a low-grade state of inflammation, resulting from enlargement of adipocyte and increased macrophage infiltration in to the adipose tissue. [53] Obese adipose tissue is characterized by abnormal production and secretion of adipokines as well as activation of inflammatory signalling in adipocytes. [54]. The fact that Visfatin possesses both cytokine-like extrinsic activity (PBEF) and an enzymatic intrinsic activity (NAMPT) is a determinant in the physiology and patho-physiology of obesity and metabolic disorders. [55][56]

Conclusion

Obesity has become a major worldwide health problem and is linked to a chronic low-grade inflammatory state which contributes to the development of obesity-associated disorders and metabolic dysfunction. Obesity is becoming a serious global issue due to its negative impact on health and its contributions to mortality and morbidity.

Our study finding suggests that the mean serum Visfatin level was significantly higher in obese (129.1 \pm 21.4)pg/ml and overweight subjects (100.8 \pm 29.9)pg/ml in comparison to normal weight subjects (82.8 \pm 26.5)pg/ml with p value equal to < 0.012 . The significant increase level of visfatin in obese may be used as a diagnostic and prognostic biomarker for Insulin Resistance and metabolic syndrome.

Visfatin and Visfatin analogue may represent a druggable target for diabetic therapy due to its insulin mimetic effect in normal physiological range. Inhibitors of Visfatin (CHS-828 and FK866) may have a role in over weight and obesity to reduce insulin resistance, inflammation, oxidative

stress and neo-vascularisation. Thus, it may be used as a targeted therapy in overweight and obese individuals to reduce morbidity and its related complications.

Factors such as antioxidant rich diet, regular exercise, lifestyle modifications along with inhibitors of visfatin favours visceral fat loss might provide an important tool to reduce the burden associated with obesity and related complications.

References

- Hager A Br Med. Bull 37 (3) 287. Park 21st edition. Chapter -6. Epidemiology of chronic Non-communicable disease and conditions. 2019;445.
- World Health Organization (WHO) Controlling the global epidemic <https://www.who.int/activities/controlling-the-global-obesity-epidemic>[2020]
- Mahmoud Abdelaal ,Carel W. le Roux, Neil G. Docherty. Morbidity and mortality associated with obesity. <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/>
- World Health Organization (WHO). Obesity and Overweight. Available from <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/obesity-and-overweight> [9th June 2022]
- Mohan V, Deepa R. Obesity and abdominal obesity in Asian Indians. Indian J Med Res. 2006 May;123(5) 593-6. PMID 1687390
- Pradeepa R, Anjana RM, Joshi SR, et al. Prevalence of generalized & abdominal obesity in urban & rural India--the ICMR-INDIAB Study (Phase I) [ICMR- NDIAB-3]. Indian J Med Res. 2015;142(2) 139-150.
- Deepa M, Farooq S, Deepa R, Manjula D, Mohan V. Prevalence and significance of generalized and central body obesity in an urban Asian Indian population in Chennai, India (CURES 47)
- Mehta N, Vanani V. Obesity in India Prevalence, Implications and Management 2016
- Al-Sharbatti S, Shaikh R, Mathew E, Sreedharan J, Muttappallymalil J, Basha S. The Use of Obesity Indicators for the Prediction of Hypertension Risk among Youth in the United Arab Emirates. Iran J Public Health. 2011;40(3) 33-40. Epub 2011 Sep 30.
- Dahl, T.B.; Yndestad, A.; Skjelland, M.; et al. Increased Expression of Visfatin in Macrophages of Human Unstable Carotid and Coronary Atherosclerosis. Circulation 2007; 115: 972–980.
- Van der Veer E, Nong Z, O'Neil C, Urquhart B, Freeman D, Pickering JG. Pre-B-cell colony-enhancing factor regulates NAD⁺-dependent protein deacetylase activity and promotes vascular smooth muscle cell maturation. Circ Res 2005; 97:25-34.
- Fan H, Li X, Zheng L, Chen X, Lan Q, Wu H, et al. Abdominal obesity is strongly associated with Cardiovascular Disease and its Risk Factors in Elderly and very Elderly Community-dwelling Chinese. Sci Rep. 2016 Feb 17;6:215 21..
- Jack Wang, Waist circumference a simple, inexpensive, and reliable tool that should be included as part of physical examinations in the doctor's office, The American Journal of Clinical Nutrition, 78(5):2003, Pages 902–903
- World Health Organization (WHO). Obesity. Available from <https://www.who.int/westernpacific/health-topics/obesity> 2016
- Kinlen D, Cody D, O'Shea D. Complications of obesity. QJM. 2018 PMID 29025162
- Wang H, Chu WS, Hemphill C, Elbein SC. Human resistin gene molecular scanning and evaluation of association with insulin sensitivity and type 2 diabetes in Caucasians. J Clin Endocrinol Metab. 2002 Jun;87(6) 2520-4
- Chumlea WC, Guo S. Bioelectrical impedance and body composition present status and future direction—reply. Nutr Rev. 1994;52 323–325.
- Lukaski HC, Johnson PE, Bolonchuk WW, Lykken GI. Assessment of fat-free mass using bioelectrical impedance measurements of the human body. Am J Clin Nutr. 1985;41(4):810–817.
- Knight GS, Beddoe AH, Streat SJ, Hill GL. Body composition of two human cadavers by neutron activation and chemical analysis. Am J Physiol. 1986;250(2 Pt 1) E179–E185
- Brozek J, Grande F, Anderson JT, Keys A. Densitometric analysis of body composition revision of some quantitative assumptions. Ann N Y Acad Sci. 1963;110:113–140
- Guo SS, Chumlea WC, Roche AF, Siervogel RM. Age- and maturity- related changes in body composition during adolescence into adulthood the Fels Longitudinal Study. Int J Obes Relat Metab Disord. 1997;21(12):1167–1175
- Sun SS, Chumlea WC, Heymsfield SB, Lukaski HC, Schoeller D, Friedl K, Kuczmarski RJ, Flegal KM, Johnson CL, Hubbard VS. Development of bioelectrical impedance analysis prediction equations for body composition with the use of a multicomponent model for use in epidemiological surveys. Am J Clin Nutr. 2003;77(2) 331–340
- Roubenoff R, Kehayias JJ, Dawson-Hughes B, Heymsfield S. Use of dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry in body-composition studies not yet a gold standard! Am J Clin Nutr. 1993;58 (5) 589–591
- Kohrt WM. Body composition by DXA tried and true? Med Sci Sports Exerc. 1995;27(10) 1349–1353.

25. Goodpaster BH, Thaete FL, Kelley DE. Composition of skeletal muscle evaluated with computed tomography. *Ann N Y Acad Sci*. 2000;904: 8–24
26. Piekarski J, Goldberg HI, Royal SA, Axel L, Moss AA. Difference between liver and spleen CT numbers in the normal adult its usefulness in predicting the presence of diffuse liver disease. *Radiology*. 1980;137(3): 727–729
27. WHO. Physical status the use and interpretation of anthropometry. Geneva WHO; 1995.
28. Bogan, K.L.; Brenner, C. Nicotinic Acid, Nicotinamide, and Nicotinamide Riboside: A Molecular Evaluation of NAD+Precursor Vitamins in Human Nutrition. *Annu. Rev. Nutr*. 2008; 28:115–130.
29. Nauli AM, Matin S. Why Do Men Accumulate Abdominal Visceral Fat? *Front Physiol*. 2019 Dec 5;10 1486.
30. Garawi, Fatima & Devries, Karen &Thorogood, Nicki &Uauy, Ricardo. Global differences between women and men in the prevalence of obesity: Is there an association with gender inequality?. *European journal of clinical nutrition*. 2014; 68.
31. Atawia, Reem T.; Toque, Haroldo A.; Meghil, Mohamed M.; Benson, Tyler W.; Yiew, Nicole K.H; et al. Role of arginase 2 in systemic metabolic activity and adipose tissue fatty acid metabolism in diet-induced obese mice. *International Journal of Molecular Sciences*. 20, 6. 1462. (2019). https://digitalcommons.wustl.edu/open_access_pubs/7649
32. Sarvottam K, Ranjan P, Yadav U. Age group and gender-wise comparison of obesity indices in subjects of Varanasi. *Indian J PhysiolPharmacol* 2020;64(2):109-17.
33. Khan S, Nauman H, Saher S, Imtiaz, H. A., Bibi, A., Sajid, H., Khan, T. M., Mumtaz, M., &Bibi, S. Gender difference in obesity prevalence among general population of Lahore, Pakistan. *European Journal of Medical and Health Sciences*, 2021; 3(3): 55–58.
34. Mabrouk R, Ghareeb H, Shehab A, Omar K, El-Kabarity RH, Soliman DA, et al. Serum visfatin, resistin and IL-18 in A group of Egyptian obese diabetic and nondiabetic individuals. *Egypt J Immunol*. 2013; 20(1) 1-11.
35. Stepien M, Stepien A, Wlazel RN, Paradowski M, Rizzo M, Banach M, Rysz J. Predictors of insulin resistance in patients with obesity a pilot study. *Angiology*. 2014 Jan;65(1) 22-30.
36. Kang YE, Kim JM, Joung KH, Lee JH, You BR, Choi MJ, Ryu MJ, Ko YB, Lee MA, Lee J, Ku BJ, Shong M, Lee KH, Kim HJ. The Roles of Adipokines, Proinflammatory Cytokines, and Adipose Tissue Macrophages in Obesity- Associated Insulin Resistance in Modest Obesity and Early Metabolic Dysfunction. *PLoS One* 2016; 11: e0154003
37. Dhuria S et al. Comparison of anthropometric parameters between obese and Non-obese women of Western Rajasthan. *International Journal of Biomedical Research*, 2014;5(9),54 7.
38. Fatemeh A and Farahnaz N. Lipid Profile Markers in Obese and Normal Weight Individuals and their Relation with obesity determinant. *Biological Forum – An International Journal*. 2014; 6(2): 514-518.
39. Babu SV, Jagadeesan AR, Ramalingam J. A Comparative Study of Lipid Profile in Obese and Nonobese Men attending Master Health Checkup. *Indian J Med Biochem* 2017; 21 (2): 73-75.
40. Kutlu R, Cihan FG. Comparison of the body compositions in obese and nonobese individuals Can learning body compositions motivate losing weight? *Niger J ClinPract*. 2017 Jan; 20(1) 82-87.
41. Kabir A, Miah S, Islam A. Factors influencing eating behaviour and dietary intake among resident students in a public university in Bangladesh: A qualitative study. *PLoS One*. 2018 Jun 19;13(6):e0198801. doi:10.1371/journal.pone. 0198801.
42. Mallick A.K, Ahsan M, Das B, Rai S. A correlation study of lipid profile with body mass index and waist hip ratio in Rohilkhand region. *Int J Med Res Rev* 2018; 6(03) 186-191.
43. Rajkovic, Natasa et al. —Relationship between obesity, adipocytokines and inflammatory markers in type 2 diabetes relevance for cardiovascular risk prevention. *International journal of environmental research and public health* 2014 Apr; 11, (4): 4049-65.
44. Montazerifar F, Bolouri A, Paghalea RS, Mahani MK, Karajibani M. Obesity, serum resistin and leptin levels linked to coronary artery disease. *Arq Bras Cardiol*. 2016; 107: 348–53.
45. Jurdana M, Petelin A, ČerneličBizjak M, Bizjak M, Biolo G, Jenko-Pražnikar Z. Increased visfatin levels in obesity and its association with anthropometric/biochemical parameters, physical activity and nutrition. *e-SPEN Journal*. 2013; 8:e59-e67.
46. Nourbakhsh, M., Nourbakhsh, M., Gholinejad, Z., &Razzaghy-Azar, M. Visfatin in obese children and adolescents and its association with insulin resistance and metabolic syndrome. *Scandinavian Journal of Clinical and Laboratory Investigation*, 2015; 75(2): 183–188.
47. Souvannavong-Vilivong X, Sitticharoon C, Klinjampa R, Keadkraichaiwat I, Sripong C,

- Chatree S et al. Placental expressions and serum levels of adiponectin, visfatin, and omentin in GDM. *ActaDiabetologica*. 2019 Oct 1;5 6(10):1121-1131.
48. Alnowihi SM, Al Doghaither HA, Osman NN. Serum visfatin concentration and its relationship with sex hormones in obese Saudi women. *Int J Health Sci (Qassim)*. 2020 May-Jun; 14(3):9-13.
49. Khanna D, Khanna S, Khanna P, Kahar P, Patel BM. Obesity: A Chronic Low-Grade Inflammation and Its Markers. *Cureus*. 2022 Feb 28; 14(2):e22711.
50. Zhang Y, Huo Y, He W, Liu S, Li H, Li L. Visfatin is regulated by interleukin6 and affected by the PPAR γ pathway in BeWo cells. *Mol Med Rep*. 2019; 19: 400-406.
51. Moschen AR, Kaser A, Enrich B, et al. Visfatin, an adipocytokine with proinflammatory and immunomodulating properties. *J Immunol* 2007; 178: 1748-1758
52. Chen MP, Chung FM, Chang DM, Tsai JC, Huang HF, Shin SJ, Lee YJ. Elevated plasma level of visfatin/pre-B cell colony-enhancing factor in patients with type 2 diabetes mellitus. *J Clin Endocrinol Metab*. 2006; 91: 295-299.
53. Dogru T, Sonmez A, Tasci I, et al. Visfatin in obesity-induced Plasma visfatin levels in patients with newly diagnosed and untreated type 2 diabetes mellitus and impaired glucose tolerance. *Diabetes Res ClinPract*. 2007; 76: 24-29.
54. Ramalingam, L., Oh, E., and Thurmond, D. C. Novel roles for insulin receptor (IR) in adipocytes and skeletal muscle cells via new and unexpected substrates. *Cell Mol. Life Sci*. 2013; 70: 2815–2834.
55. Luk T, Malam Z, Marshall JC. Pre-B cell colony-enhancing factor (PBEF) / visfatin: a novel mediator of innate immunity. *J Leukoc Biol*. 2008; 83: 804-816.
56. Cignarelli A, Genchi VA, Perrini S, Natalicchio A, Laviola L, Giorgino F. Insulin and Insulin Receptors in Adipose Tissue Development. *Int J Mol Sci*. 2019 Feb 11; 20(3):759.